

Teachers' Assessment in the Implementation of Modular Learning

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Abstract— This study was conducted to determine the assessment of teachers of Enrile Vocational High School on the implementation of modular learning. A descriptive survey was utilized involving 50 secondary school teachers. Data were analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics. Results reveal that the different dimensions for the implementation of the modular learning, such as technical elements, teachers' preparedness, self-learning module, teachers' support, and material resources, are evident. Teachers and the schools in which they teach have been prepared technically. Additionally, teachers expressed their readiness to perform their assigned tasks and functions concerning the teaching and learning processes under the new normal education. The Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) are dependable, and their reproduction and release are seamless. Finally, teachers receive the necessary training and skill development webinars to perform their jobs effectively.

Keywords— *Modular Learning, Distance Learning, Department of Education, COVID-19 pandemic, Secondary School*

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic can be seen as it affects nearly all nations in all sectors and spheres of life. Education is one of the sectors that has been particularly hard hit by the pandemic. COVID-19 infected schools not only in Wuhan, China but also in 188 other countries (Toquero, 2020). In the Philippines, as part of President Rodrigo Duterte's order to impose a community quarantine in order to contain the spread of COVID-19, face-to-face classes have been suspended. However, given the critical role education plays in the society, learning should never cease. As a result, the Department of Education (DepEd) pioneered distance education. Distance Learning is a mode of instruction in which learning occurs between the teacher and learners who are geographically separated during instruction. This mode of instruction is classified into three distinct categories: modular distance learning (MDL), online distance learning (ODL), and television/radio-based instruction (Jayani, 2021).

Modular education is the most widely used form of distance education in the Philippines (Cascayan et al., 2020; Anzaldo, 2020). This mode of instruction is currently being implemented in all public schools because, according to a survey conducted by DepEd, learning through printed and

digital modules was identified as the most preferred method of distance learning by parents of children enrolled this academic year (DepEd, 2020). This is also in consideration of learners, particularly those in rural areas where online learning is not available. As a result, almost 13 million public school students, or 59% of roughly 22 million enrollees this school year, were enrolled under the modular learning (San Antonio, 2020).

Students were provided with self-learning modules (SLMs) as part of the DepEd's printed modular learning system. Teachers distributed SLMs to students on a quarterly basis. This means that students received four (4) sets of SLMs over the course of an academic year. SLMs were distributed to parents prior to the start of classes in this configuration. For students whose parents are unable to pick them up from school, designated pick-up points were established in their barangays. Distribution occurred at least four times throughout the school year. Teachers collected completed activity sheets from parents. They were required to submit activity sheets to teachers at their respective schools or designated pick-up locations (Department of Education, 2020). Adjustments and paradigm shifts toward students, teachers, and even parents were observed in this new normal in education.

However, despite the shift in the learning modality, teachers remain as the main facilitators of learning, which means that they are the responsible school personnel in-charge of the teaching-learning process. However, recent articles and studies showed some pressing issues and concerns brought about by the implementation of the distance-based learning, such as the modular learning modality. According to the Teachers' Dignity Coalition (TDC, 2020), one of the most pressing concerns raised by field teachers is the need for them to develop modules for the implementation of blended/distance learning when specialists from the Department of Education should be doing so. In addition, Basilio (2020) stated that teachers have raised a myriad of concerns about the modular learning preparations and expressed disappointment. In addition, reproduction costs are a significant issue, as schools are being forced to raise funds in such a short period of time, and some teachers are being forced to report to school as late as 11:00 p.m. in order to complete the printing on time. After a year of implementation, it is then important to conduct a study assessing the initial implementation of such learning modality,

especially since this kind of set-up will continue until the country reaches herd immunity. Hence, this study was conducted.

II. METHODS

This study utilized a quantitative type of research employing descriptive survey method. The respondents of the study were the 50 secondary school teachers of Enrile Vocational High School.

The study utilized a questionnaire with two parts. The first part illicit the profile of the respondents as to the following: gender, age, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, field of specialization, educational level, living condition, mode of transportation, and number of seminars attended related to modular education. The second part of the questionnaire consists of items assessing the implementation of modular learning in the Department of Education (DepEd), which was lifted from Guimalon, Alon, and Camsa (2021). The tool consists of 50 items and is divided into seven dimensions: Technical Elements (10 items), Teachers' Preparedness (10 items), Self-Learning Modules (10 items), Material Resources (10 items), and Teachers' Support (10 items), which were answered by the respondents from 4 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree).

Data Analysis

Frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents.

Weighted mean was used to determine the assessment of the respondents on modular learning with the following range and qualitative descriptions:

Range	Qualitative Descriptions
3.50-4.00	Highly Evident
2.50-3.49	Evident
1.50-2.49	Less Evident
1.00-1.49	Not Evident

Independent Sample T-Test and One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to determine significant difference on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning when grouped according to profile variables.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	15	30.00
Female	35	70.00
Age		
21-30 years old	12	24.00
31-40 years old	20	40.00
41-50 years old	10	20.00
51 years old and above	8	16.00
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	32	64.00
With Master's Degree	17	34.00
With Doctorate Degree	1	2.00
Number of Years in Teaching		
1-5 Years	21	42.00
6-10 Years	18	38.00
11-15 Years	9	18.00
16 years and above	2	4.00
Field of Specialization		
BSED English	8	16.00
BSED Mathematics	8	16.00
BSED Science	8	16.00
BSED Filipino	6	12.00
BSED Social Studies	7	35.00
BSED MAPEH	5	10.00
BSTEd	3	6.00
Bachelor of Arts	3	6.00
Health Related Program	2	4.00
Living Condition		
Living in Enrile, Cagayan	38	72.00
Living Outside Enrile, Cagayan	12	24.00
Mode of Transportation		
With Motorcycle	25	50.00
With Car	14	28.00
None	11	22.00
Number of Seminars Attended Related to Modular Education		
More than 3	2	4.00
Two	8	16.00
One	35	70.00
None	5	10.00

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents. It can be shown from the table that in terms of gender, there are more female than male respondents in the study. Along age,

more than half of the respondents are young and middle-aged teachers who are below 40 years old. In addition, many of the respondents are still new in the profession since many of them are teaching in the school for less than five (5) years. Along field specialization, almost all of the respondents are graduates of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED). Meanwhile, majority of the respondents reside in Enrile, Cagayan where the school is located. In addition, most of the respondents have their motorcycles and cars as their mode of transportation. Finally, majority of the respondents only attended one training/seminar related to modular education.

Table 2a. Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning along Technical Elements

Technical Elements	Mean	Qualitative Description
The school is technologically prepared for modular learning modality.	2.74	Evident
There are laptops or computers available in the school.	3.10	Evident
Modules are available in the Department of Education links and ready to download.	3.26	Evident
Using of smart phones, laptops, and computers for downloading of modules is easy for teachers.	3.17	Evident
Teachers have a reasonable level of competence with computers.	3.10	Evident
The geographical location of school is considered as hotspot to access strong internet connection.	2.95	Evident
Internet access is also available all the time in school.	2.40	Less Evident
Electricity is also available in all classrooms.	3.60	Highly Evident
Printers and photocopier machines are available in school.	3.12	Evident
Category Mean	3.10	Evident

Table 2a shows the assessment of the respondents on modular learning along technical elements. It can be shown from the results that two items were assessed by the respondents as highly evident. These include the following: electricity is also available in all classrooms and the school provides contact tracing record for parents entering in school. Electricity is a basic necessity in all institutions, especially among schools, even before the pandemic. Today, there is a need for all classrooms to have electricity since teachers will be working on the preparations of their modules in every classroom to avoid overcrowding and as a way for social distancing of teachers in the school. Meanwhile, contact tracing is an essential requirement to all establishments and institutions prior to their operation, as stipulated by the IATF and the Department of Education (DepEd) for monitoring and contact purposes. Meanwhile, all other items were rated by the respondents as evident. This could mean that the school and

teachers are ready to implement this kind of learning modality along technical readiness. Specifically, teachers have their own laptops, computers, and cellphones, and they are technically capable of adopting and utilizing these technologies. According to Castroverde and Alcalá (2020), 87 percent of 700,000 teachers nationwide who responded to a recent survey of DepEd have laptops or computers at home, while 13 percent have none. Only 41% of those with gadgets have an internet signal in their area but no connection of their own. Meanwhile, only one item, which is internet access is also available all the time in school, was assessed by teachers. Espineli (2021) stressed that one of the limitations of distance education is internet connectivity, especially since many schools, mainly located in the provinces, have limited internet connection. As a result, teachers provide for their own connection, such as prepaid wifi modems that can be carried in the school. In general, the assessment of the respondents on modular learning along technical elements is evident.

Table 2b. Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning along Teacher Preparedness

Teacher Preparedness	Mean	Qualitative Description
Teachers were prepared to conduct distance learning education in times of COVID-19.	3.32	Evident
Teachers were prepared to use printed modules as a tool for learning at home.	3.19	Evident
Teachers are monitoring and tacking the learners' accomplishment of the task provided in the SLMs.	3.40	Evident
Teachers had capacity building on distance learning education management for teachers.	2.80	Evident
Teachers had a proper training in the use of technology needed for learning dissemination.	2.68	Evident
The school has provided the regulation and policies on the use of modular learning.	3.40	Evident
The school has provided supplementary materials for modular learning.	2.70	Evident
Teachers are well-oriented in delivering modules.	3.55	Highly Evident
The school has designated skeletal workforce for the COVID-19 pandemic.	3.52	Highly Evident
Virtual communication is done for more information from the Department of Education.	3.40	Evident
Category Mean	3.20	Evident

Table 2b shows the assessment of the respondents on modular learning along teacher preparedness. Specifically, two items were assessed by the respondents as highly evident.

These include the following: teachers are well-oriented in delivering modules and the school has designated skeletal workforce for the COVID-19 pandemic. This could mean that prior to the implementation of modular learning, DepEd, through the different SDOs and Districts, implemented different orientation programs among teachers. Meanwhile, along the implementation of skeletal workforce, the school complied with the IATF policies and guidelines with regard to the reduced number of teachers reporting in the school, especially that until this moment, the province is under the stricter Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine (MECQ) where institutions are only allowed to have at least 50% of the employees to report. Meanwhile, all other items were assessed by the respondents as evident. This implies that teachers are adequately trained and oriented to perform their assigned tasks and functions in times of pandemic. San Antonio (2020) stressed that DepEd did many orientation and readiness programs for teachers with regard to the implementation of distance-based learning before the school year 2020-2021 starts. In addition, Cos et al. (2021) also emphasized that apart from the training, there are also local initiatives from division and regional offices through which teachers receive training. In general, the respondents viewed the teacher's preparedness in modular learning as evident.

Table 2c. Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning along Self-Learning Modules

Self-Learning Modules	Mean	Qualitative Description
All printed modules are available to be distributed.	2.49	Less Evident
There is a rapid reproduction of SLMs because school has enough printing equipment.	2.48	Less Evident
Releasing of SLMs are on time because of enough school supplies.	2.46	Less Evident
Reproduction cost is not a big problem as schools have enough funds.	2.40	Less Evident
There is no excess copy of SLMs because all parents were able to receive it.	2.82	Evident
Self-learning modules have no erroneous contents.	2.64	Evident
Key concepts on SLMs are not limited and it is deepened.	3.10	Evident
The language use and degree of difficulties to different types of learners were considered.	3.15	Evident
The activities and exercises are suited to the multiple abilities of learners.	3.10	Evident
Assessment designs in the SLMs are sensitive to the ability, interest, developmental preparedness, and available resources at home.	3.12	Evident
Category Mean	2.78	Evident

Table 2c shows the assessment of the respondents on modular learning along self-learning modules. It can be shown from the results that most of the items were assessed by the respondents as evident. These items focused on the contents of the SLMs provided by DepEd. This could show that prior to the transmission of the SLMs to different schools, DepEd Central Office, through its Quality Assurance section, ensures that all modules are properly checked and validated. The findings would mean that printed modules include key concepts that are not limited and are expanded upon, grammar checked, and undergone series of validations responsive to the needs of diverse learners. Briones (2020) stressed that SLMs and other alternative modes of delivery are in place to address the unique needs, circumstances, and resources of each and every learner, and to ensure that basic education is accessible despite the current COVID-19 crisis. Meanwhile, it can also be gleaned from the table that four items were assessed by the respondents as less evident. These items focused more on the distribution and reproduction of modules. Toquero (2020) claimed that it is understood that no teacher will be obliged to prepare modules since SLMs will be coming from the central office. However, during the start of classes, some subjects do not have available SLMs, and in the end, teachers were the ones writing and developing their modules to ensure that the school year will take place. In general, teachers' assessment on modular learning along self-learning modules is evident.

Table 2d. Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning along Teacher Support

Teacher Support	Mean	Qualitative Description
Teachers can easily finish printing, sorting, and organizing SLMs for the succeeding weeks.	3.55	Highly Evident
Teachers are safe to do home visitation when needed.	3.48	Evident
Teachers are not facing dangerous path everyday within modular learning set up.	2.70	Evident
Establishing a network of communication among stakeholders such as parents for support at home is easy.	2.60	Evident
Checking and evaluating children's output from module exercises is not a big problem.	2.45	Less Evident
Monitoring children's learning is easy.	2.48	Less Evident
Giving instructions to the parents is easeful.	2.40	Less Evident
Managing stress caused by community quarantine at home and rush reproduction of SLMs is simple.	2.45	Less Evident
Teachers had virtual training and skills development to face the new learning modality.	3.10	Evident

Beating the deadlines and requirements set by the school administrators is easy.	2.32	Less Evident
Category Mean	2.75	Evident

Table 2d shows the assessment of the respondents on modular learning along teacher support. It can be shown from the table that the highest item that was assessed by the respondents as highly evident is that teachers can easily finish printing, sorting, and organizing SLMs for the succeeding weeks. Since SLMs are given on a weekly or monthly basis, teachers need to prepare all the SLMs to ensure that no problems and difficulties will be experienced during the distribution of SLMs in different communities. In addition, the other four items were assessed by the teachers as evident, which focused on the role of teachers during the implementation of modular learning, such as doing home visitation, going to different communities for the distribution and retrieval of SLMs despite its health risks brought by the COVID-19, forging partnerships with parents, and engagement to professional development programs related to the implementation of this new learning modality.

It is important to note that half of the items under this dimension were assessed by the respondents as less evident. These items focused on the instructional and pedagogical aspects of teacher support, such as checking and evaluating students' output, monitoring student progress, giving instructions to parents, managing stress caused by the pandemic, and beating deadlines and requirements set by the department. Because SLMs are given either monthly or quarterly, it is difficult for teachers to check easily due to the bulk of papers from their almost 300 students. In addition, there is also a problem encountered by teachers with regard to giving instructions to the parents since, in the new normal, parents play a crucial role in the success of students since they are now considered major facilitators of learning to their children. San Antonio (2020) claimed that another factor that most likely affects the effectiveness of distance learning activities is the presence of an active communication mechanism between teachers, parents or guardians, and learners. Because of the constant communication, doubts, confusions, and uncertainties, as well as the difficult activities or problems assigned to be undertaken and solved by learners, will be effectively addressed.

Table 2e. Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning along Material Resources

Material Resources	Mean	Qualitative Description
The school has enough budget for reproduction.	2.85	Evident
Overwhelming printing causal equipment is not a big problem because school has a lot of resources.	2.70	Evident
The ability to generate more resources to supply the printing	3.10	Evident

materials in school is easy.		
Schools do not need to solicit private donations just to jumpstart the reproduction of modules.	2.60	Evident
There is an adequate financial support from the Department of Education.	3.27	Evident
There is a balance in expenditures resulting to sufficient resources and finances.	3.10	Evident
There are more donations from the different private organizations.	3.25	Evident
Local Government Unit supports the school for the SLMs reproduction.	3.40	Evident
Local community and government stakeholders supported schools by providing Technology and multi-media like desktops, laptops, printers, and other electronic devices such as tablets, e-books, and multimedia board.	3.48	Evident
Financial assistance for the reproduction of SLMs is fully utilized.	3.69	Highly Evident
Category Mean	3.14	Evident

Table 2e shows the assessment of the respondents on modular learning along material resources. It can be shown from the results that the highest item being assessed by the respondents is that financial assistance for the reproduction of SLMs is fully utilized. This could mean that the school really prioritized the expenses for the reproduction of SLMs for the school year as reflected in the school MOOE. This also implies that the school is compliant with DepEd Order No. 18 series of 2020, which establishes the guidelines for the provision of learning resources in implementing BE-LCP. Additionally, it contains guidelines for the release, use, and liquidation of support funds used to print and deliver self-learning modules and other learning resources. Meanwhile, all other items were assessed by the respondents as evident. Sevilla (2020) stated that DepEd had already realigned, reprioritized, and utilized the Special Education Fund to meet the new off-school learning requirements, following the support of Local Government Units (LGUs).

Table 2f. Summary Table on the Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning

Dimensions	Mean	Qualitative Description
Technical Elements	3.10	Evident
Teacher Preparedness	3.20	Evident
Self-Learning Modules	2.78	Evident
Teacher Support	2.75	Evident
Material Resources	3.14	Evident
Overall Mean	2.99	Evident

Table 2f shows the summary table on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning. It can be shown from the table that the different dimensions for the implementation of modular learning, such as technical elements, teacher preparedness, self-learning modules, teacher support, and material resources, are evident. Teachers and the schools in which they teach have been prepared technically. Additionally, teachers expressed their readiness to perform their assigned tasks and functions in connection with the teaching and learning processes under the new normal education. The Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) are dependable, and their reproduction and release are seamless. Finally, teachers receive the necessary training and skill development webinars to perform their jobs effectively.

Table 3. Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning when grouped According to Profile Variables

Profile Variables	t-Value/ F-Value	P- value	Decision
Gender	1.250	.485	Not Significant
Age	6.850	.000	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	.580	.580	Not Significant
Number of Years in Teaching	-.487	.682	Not Significant
Field of Specialization	1.256	.110	Not Significant
Educational Level	.875	.250	Not Significant
Living Conditions	5.423	.001	Significant
Mode of Transportation	5.142	.000	Significant
Number of Seminars Attended Related to Modular Education	.850	.410	Not Significant

*significant at .05 level

Table 3 shows the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning when grouped according to profile variables. The table shows that there is no significant difference on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning when grouped according to gender, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, field of specialization, educational level, and number of seminars attended related to modular education. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This could mean that their assessment on modular learning does not vary regardless of these profile variables.

Meanwhile, a significant difference exists on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning when grouped according to age, living conditions, and mode of transportation. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the assessment of the respondents on modular learning varies regardless of these profile variables.

Table 3a. Post-Hoc Test Analysis on the Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning when grouped According to Age

Age Group	Mean	21-30	31-40	41-50	50 and above
21-30 years old	3.15	1			
31-40 years old	3.08	.650	1		
41-50 years old	2.94	.000*	.480	1	
50 years old and above	2.80	.000*	.450	.885	1

Table 3a shows the post-hoc test analysis on the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning when grouped according to age. It can be shown from the results that a significant difference exists between teachers who are 21-30 years old and teachers who are 41 years old and above. This could mean that young teachers have a higher level of assessment on modular learning than senior teachers. Young teachers are considered more adaptive and flexible, especially along technological innovations and changes, while senior teachers have difficulties in embracing educational changes and innovations (Oke & Frenandez, 2020); in this case, the introduction of distance-based education such as the modular learning.

Table 3b. Post-Hoc Test Analysis on the Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning when grouped According to Living Conditions

Living Condition	Mean	t-value	P-value	Decision
Living in Enrile, Cagayan	3.35	5.423	.001	Significant
Living Outside Enrile, Cagayan	2.54			

Table 3b shows the post-hoc test analysis on the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning when grouped according to living conditions. It can be shown from the results that teachers living in Enrile, Cagayan, where the school is located, have a higher level of assessment than those teachers residing outside the municipality. This can be attributed to the fact that since modular learning requires an extensive partnership with the community, teachers from the said place are already familiar with and have also built relationships with the locals, unlike those who are not from the said locale.

Table 3c. Post-Hoc Test Analysis on the Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Respondents on Modular Learning when grouped According to Mode of Transportation

Mode of Transportation	Mean	Motorcycle	Car	None
Motorcycle	3.14	1		
Car	3.22	.670	1	
None	2.62	.002*	.001*	1

Table 3c shows the post-hoc test analysis on the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents on modular learning when grouped according to mode of transportation. It can be shown from the results that teachers who own motorcycles or cars have a higher level of assessment on modular learning than those teachers who do not have vehicles. This can be attributed to the fact that due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a limited number of public utility vehicles plying in the municipality and, at the same time, have a higher amount of fares due to limitation of occupants. In addition, since modular learning requires movement from different communities for the distribution and retrieval of SLMs, teachers who do not own personal vehicles may have difficulties with their transportation, unlike those teachers who own either a motorcycle or a car.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that the adaptation of modular distance learning at Enrile Vocational High School yields both positive and negative views from the teachers. Despite the readiness of the school and teachers on the implementation of the said modality from technological and teacher preparedness to reproduction, distribution, and retrieval of SLMs, teachers still raised some difficulties and concerns, especially along internet connectivity, release and reproduction of SLMs, and instructional and pedagogical practices in modular learning.

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